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Determining Criteria Weights in MCDM Problems Using the Z-AHP Method

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) method used to determine the criteria weights in the integrated fuzzy multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) approach developed by Erkayman et al. [1] for third-party logistics (3PL) provider selection has been re-examined using Z-numbers. The original model involves defining supplier selection criteria, determining their weights via fuzzy AHP, and ranking alternatives using the fuzzy TOPSIS method. A panel of experts, managers, and academics selected six key criteria—price, overall reputation, customer service, on-time delivery, information technologies, and flexibility—from an initial list of 30, and evaluated five alternatives out of 15 candidates. To capture the uncertainty in expert judgments, triangular fuzzy numbers were used in linguistic assessments.

Z-numbers, proposed by Lotfi A. Zadeh [2], differ from classical fuzzy numbers by representing not only the uncertainty of a value but also the confidence level associated with that value. Mathematically, a Z-number is represented as $Z=(A,B)$, where A is a fuzzy number reflecting the decision-maker's assessment (e.g., the importance of a criterion), and B is another fuzzy number representing the degree of confidence in that assessment. Thus, Z-numbers more realistically capture the complexity of decision-makers' judgments by simultaneously accounting for both uncertainty and confidence levels. This study's primary contribution is the integration of the Z-number approach into the AHP step for calculating criteria weights in the previously described fuzzy MCDM framework.

In this paper, the process of determining criteria weights has been restructured using Z-numbers. First, the relative importance levels of the six main criteria determined by the decision-makers were represented as a pairwise comparison matrix whose elements are Z-numbers. The comparisons were made using linguistic expressions. The Z-numbers, which constitute the elements of the pairwise comparison matrix, were obtained by assigning hypothetical confidence levels to the triangular fuzzy numbers corresponding to these linguistic expressions. The resulting Z-number-based pairwise comparison matrix was analyzed using an AHP method adapted for Z-numbers,

leading to the calculation of each criterion's weight as a Z-number that simultaneously incorporates both uncertainty and confidence levels.

This approach allows for the integral incorporation of both uncertainty and confidence levels in the decision-makers' subjective judgments, thereby enabling a more precise and reliable determination of criteria weights. As a result, the quality and robustness of the obtained weights are enhanced—particularly in decision-making contexts where expert opinions play a critical role. The proposed Z-AHP approach enhances the reliability and robustness of decision-making in expert-based multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) processes.

1 INTRODUCTION

The selection of third-party logistics (3PL) providers represents a critical decision-making challenge for companies seeking to enhance supply chain performance in today's increasingly competitive and uncertain business environment. This decision typically involves multiple, often conflicting criteria—such as cost, reputation, customer service, on-time delivery, information technology, and flexibility—and is therefore well-suited to multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) approaches [3,4].

Among the many MCDM techniques, the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and the Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS), particularly in their fuzzy extensions, have been widely adopted to better address the inherent uncertainty and subjectivity in expert evaluations [5,6]. In this context, ErKayman et al. (2012) proposed an integrated fuzzy MCDM model for 3PL provider selection, combining fuzzy AHP for determining criteria weights and fuzzy TOPSIS for ranking alternatives [1]. In their framework, a panel of experts, managers, and academics identified the most relevant criteria from a broader set and evaluated candidate providers using linguistic terms represented by triangular fuzzy numbers, thus incorporating uncertainty into the evaluation process.

While fuzzy set theory effectively captures vagueness in human judgment, it does not explicitly account for the reliability or confidence level associated with these judgments. To address this shortcoming, Zadeh (2011) introduced the concept of Z-numbers, which enhance fuzzy numbers by pairing each with a confidence measure—offering a more comprehensive representation of uncertainty [2]. Since their introduction, Z-numbers have been successfully applied in various decision-making contexts to improve the robustness and realism of MCDM models [7,8].

Building upon this foundation, the present study revisits the criteria weighting stage of the fuzzy MCDM framework proposed by ErKayman et al. (2012), integrating Z-numbers into the AHP method. By representing both the uncertainty and the confidence level in pairwise comparisons, the proposed Z-AHP approach aims to improve the precision and reliability of criteria weights, which are crucial for effective 3PL provider selection.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides the necessary preliminaries and theoretical background; Section 3 presents the arithmetic operations and sorting steps with Z-numbers; Section 4 details the application of the proposed methodology to the target problem in a Z-number environment. Finally, Section 5 presents conclusions and summarizes implications for future research and applications.

2 PRELIMINARIES

This section introduces the fundamental concepts and methodologies that form the basis of the current study. It begins by emphasizing the significance of Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) methods in addressing complex decision problems, such as the selection of third-party logistics (3PL) providers. Next, Fuzzy Set Theory and Triangular Fuzzy Numbers (TFNs), which facilitate the modeling of uncertain and linguistic information, are introduced. Subsequently, the Analytic

Hierarchy Process (AHP), a widely adopted MCDM technique, is discussed. Finally, the concept of Z-numbers—enabling the simultaneous modeling of uncertainty and the associated confidence—is examined.

2.1 Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM)

Modern supply chains have become increasingly complex due to heightened competition and globalization. Within this challenging environment, the selection of third-party logistics (3PL) providers through outsourcing has emerged as a strategically critical decision. This selection process inherently constitutes a multi-criteria decision problem, involving the evaluation of alternatives against multiple, often conflicting criteria such as cost, quality, delivery time, flexibility, and technological capability [9]. To systematically address such problems, a variety of Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) methods have been developed.

MCDM encompasses a range of methodologies designed to select, rank, or classify a finite set of alternatives based on predefined criteria [10]. The literature documents the successful application of numerous MCDM techniques—including AHP, TOPSIS, VIKOR, and ANP—to the 3PL provider selection problem [11]. In this study, the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is employed as the primary methodology, given its strength in managing hierarchical problem structures and its capacity to quantify decision-makers' judgments effectively.

2.2 Fuzzy Set Theory and Triangular Fuzzy Numbers (TFNs)

Decision-making processes, particularly those reliant on human judgment, frequently involve imprecise, vague, and linguistic information. Traditional mathematical tools often fall short in effectively modeling such uncertainties. To address this limitation, Fuzzy Set Theory—introduced by Zadeh (1965) [12]—offers a robust mathematical framework for representing ambiguity. Unlike classical binary logic, which restricts membership to values of 0 or 1, fuzzy sets allow elements to possess degrees of membership within the continuous interval [0, 1].

Fuzzy numbers are specialized fuzzy sets defined over the real number domain, commonly used to represent linguistic expressions such as “approximately 5” or “low cost.” Due to their simplicity and effectiveness in applications, one of the most commonly used types of fuzzy numbers is the Triangular Fuzzy Number (TFN). A TFN is defined by a triplet of real numbers, $\tilde{A} = (l, m, u)$, where l , m , and u denote the lower limit, the most plausible (modal) value, and the upper limit, respectively. The membership function, $\mu_{\tilde{A}}(x)$, is defined as follows:

$$\mu_{\tilde{A}}(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{x-l}{m-l}, & l \leq x < m \\ \frac{u-x}{u-m}, & m \leq x < u \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

For two positive TFNs, $\tilde{A}_1 = (l_1, m_1, u_1)$ and $\tilde{A}_2 = (l_2, m_2, u_2)$, the basic arithmetic operations are as follows:

- *Addition:* $\tilde{A}_1 \oplus \tilde{A}_2 = (l_1 + l_2, m_1 + m_2, u_1 + u_2)$ (1)
- *Subtraction:* $\tilde{A}_1 \ominus \tilde{A}_2 = (l_1 - u_2, m_1 - m_2, u_1 - l_2)$ (2)
- *Multiplication:* $\tilde{A}_1 \otimes \tilde{A}_2 = (l_1 l_2, m_1 m_2, u_1 u_2)$ (3)
- *Division:* $\tilde{A}_1 \oslash \tilde{A}_2 = (l_1/u_2, m_1/m_2, u_1/l_2)$ (4)

2.3 The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)

Developed by Thomas L. Saaty in 1980 [13], the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is a widely used and effective Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) method that leverages human perception and judgment to simplify complex decision problems. AHP decomposes a problem into a hierarchical structure consisting of the overall goal, criteria and sub-criteria, and decision alternatives. This framework enables decision-makers to perform pairwise comparisons of elements within each level of the hierarchy. The key steps of the AHP methodology are as follows:

- i. *Structuring the Hierarchy*: The decision problem is modelled as a hierarchy with the overall goal at the top, main and sub-criteria at intermediate levels, and decision alternatives at the bottom.
- ii. *Constructing Pairwise Comparison Matrices*: Elements at each level are compared in pairs with respect to their importance to the element at the level above. The comparisons are made using Saaty's fundamental scale of 1 to 9.
- iii. *Calculating Priority Vectors*: From each comparison matrix, a priority vector is derived, indicating the relative weights (priorities) of the elements. This is typically done by normalizing the eigenvector corresponding to the largest eigenvalue of the matrix.
- iv. *Consistency Analysis*: A Consistency Ratio (CR) is calculated to measure the consistency of the decision-maker's judgments. A $CR < 0.10$ is generally considered to indicate an acceptable level of consistency.
- v. *Synthesizing Overall Priorities*: The overall priorities of the alternatives are calculated by aggregating the weights throughout the hierarchy, and the alternative with the highest overall priority is identified as the best choice.

2.4 Z-Numbers

While fuzzy numbers used in traditional decision-making methods such as AHP effectively model the ambiguity inherent in linguistic expressions, they fall short in capturing the reliability of the information or the credibility of the expert providing it. For instance, when two experts both assess a criterion as "important," this does not necessarily imply that they share the same level of confidence in their evaluations. To address this limitation, Zadeh (2011) introduced the concept of Z-numbers.

A Z-number is defined as an ordered pair of fuzzy numbers, $Z = (\tilde{A}, \tilde{B})$.

- *The \tilde{A} -component*: A fuzzy number representing the constraint or the primary value of interest. For example, "the importance of a criterion is 'high'."
- *The \tilde{B} -component*: A fuzzy number denoting the reliability or certainty of the information in the \tilde{A} -component. For example, "the confidence in this judgment is 'very high'."

Thus, a Z-number can be interpreted as the probability of "the value of X is \tilde{A} " being \tilde{B} , adding a richer layer of information to the decision-making process [14]. Traditional approaches, before performing computations with Z-numbers, first convert them into a single fuzzy number, which leads to a loss of the valuable reliability information contained in the \tilde{B} -component. In contrast, this study employs a methodology that performs arithmetic operations directly on Z-numbers, thereby preserving the full informational content of both components. The details of this approach are presented in the following section.

3 OPERATIONS WITH Z-NUMBERS

The primary advantage of Z-numbers in decision-making lies in their ability to simultaneously capture both the uncertainty associated with a variable's value (the \tilde{A} -component) and the reliability of the information supporting that value (the \tilde{B} -component). However, in order to fully utilize this enriched information structure, it is essential to employ arithmetic operations that are performed

directly on Z-numbers, rather than relying on indirect methods that reduce Z-numbers to conventional fuzzy numbers—an approach that inevitably leads to information loss.

Beyond arithmetic computation, the ability to compare and rank Z-numbers is equally crucial for decision-making processes, as it facilitates the prioritization of alternatives or criteria by considering both the value of the information and its associated confidence level.

This study adopts the arithmetic framework for continuous Z-numbers developed by Aliev et al. (2016) [15], which preserves the two-component structure of Z-numbers throughout all computational stages. This approach ensures that the outputs derived from decision matrices reflect not only the evaluated values but also the aggregate reliability of the judgments from which those values are obtained.

3.1 The General Principle of Z-Arithmetic

According to Aliev et al. (2016), an arithmetic operation $*$ (e.g., addition, multiplication) performed on two Z-numbers, $Z_1 = (\tilde{A}_1, \tilde{B}_1)$ and $Z_2 = (\tilde{A}_2, \tilde{B}_2)$, results in a new Z-number, $Z_3 = (\tilde{A}_3, \tilde{B}_3)$. The core principle underlying this operation is the independent processing of the two components, where the arithmetic is conducted separately on the \tilde{A} -components and the \tilde{B} -components;

- i. *Computation of the Value Component (\tilde{A}_3):* The \tilde{A}_3 component of the resulting Z-number is obtained by applying the standard fuzzy arithmetic operation on the value components \tilde{A}_1 and \tilde{A}_2 of the original Z-numbers, using Zadeh's Extension Principle. That is, $\tilde{A}_3 = \tilde{A}_1 * \tilde{A}_2$.
- ii. *Computation of the Reliability Component (\tilde{B}_3):* The reliability component \tilde{B}_3 of the resulting Z-number is formed by combining the original reliability components \tilde{B}_1 and \tilde{B}_2 . Aliev et al. (2016) propose a complex model for this combination based on the convolution of probability density functions. However, this model is computationally intensive for practical decision-making applications.

3.2 Calculation Steps for Z-Arithmetic

In this section, the steps of arithmetic operations with continuous Z-numbers described in [15] are given.

Let $Z_1 = (\tilde{A}_1, \tilde{B}_1)$ and $Z_2 = (\tilde{A}_2, \tilde{B}_2)$ be continuous Z-numbers. Being $* \in \{\oplus, \ominus, \otimes, \oslash\}$, the steps of the

$$Z_3 = Z_1 * Z_2 = (\tilde{A}_1 * \tilde{A}_2, \tilde{B}_1 \circ \tilde{B}_2) = (\tilde{A}_3, \tilde{B}_3)$$

arithmetic operation process are as follows:

- Step 1.* The result of the operation, $\tilde{A}_3 = \tilde{A}_1 * \tilde{A}_2$, is calculated by using the appropriate equation from (1), (2), (3), or (4) for $\tilde{A}_1 = (l_1, m_1, u_1)$ and $\tilde{A}_2 = (l_2, m_2, u_2)$.
- Step 2.* Moving to the Z^+ -numbers, $R_3 = R_1 * R_2$ is calculated using the convolution $p_3 = p_1 \circ p_2$. In this study, the probability distributions p_1 and p_2 underlying R_1 and R_2 are assumed to fit the normal distribution for addition, subtraction and multiplication and the Cauchy distribution for division.
- Step 3.* The discretized $\mu_{p_j}, j = 1, 2$ membership degrees are calculated.
- Step 4.* The membership degrees of the discretized μ_{p_3} are determined with the use of $\mu_{p_3}(p_3) = \mu_{p_1}(p_1) \wedge \mu_{p_2}(p_2)$, where p_3 is the p_1 and p_2 convolution.
- Step 5.* $\mu_{B_3}(b_3) = \mu_{p_3}(p_3)$ equation is used to determine the membership function of $\mu_{B_3}(b_3)$. $b_3 = \sum_{i=1}^n \mu_{A_3}(x_i) p_3(x_i)$ equation is solved to find the base values of b_3 . The triangular fuzzy number B_3 is determined using the obtained μ_{B_3} .

So $Z_3 = (\tilde{A}_3, \tilde{B}_3)$ is calculated.

3.3 Ranking of Z-Numbers

In this section, the Z-numbers ranking algorithm by a sigmoid function based on the combination of the convex method in [16] is briefly introduced.

The Rank(Z) value of a $Z = (\tilde{A}, \tilde{B})$ Z-number, including $G = (x_{\tilde{A}^*} \times |\alpha|) + STD_{\tilde{A}^*}$, can be calculated using the formula provided below.

$$Rank(Z) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{1 + e^{-G}} & , G > 0 \\ 0 & , G = 0 \\ \frac{-1}{1 + e^{-G}} & , G < 0 \end{cases}$$

In this algorithm; α represents the conversion of \tilde{B} (reliability) into a crisp number, which is calculated according to the following formula:

$$\alpha = \frac{\int_X x \mu_{\tilde{B}}(x) dx}{\int_X \mu_{\tilde{B}}(x) dx}$$

\tilde{A}^* represents the standardized generalized version of the trapezoidal fuzzy number \tilde{A} . The defuzzified value of \tilde{A}^* , denoted by $x_{\tilde{A}^*}$, is calculated according to the following formula, which combines the definition of the mean value and the convex combination:

$$x_{\tilde{A}^*} = \frac{\lambda(a_2^* + a_3^*) + (1 - \lambda)(a_1^* + a_4^*)}{\lambda\delta_1 + (1 - \lambda)\delta_2}$$

$STD_{\tilde{A}^*}$ represents the spread value of \tilde{A}^* and is calculated as follows.

$$STD_{\tilde{A}^*} = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda((a_2^* - x_{\tilde{A}^*})^2 + (a_3^* - x_{\tilde{A}^*})^2) + (1 - \lambda)((a_1^* - x_{\tilde{A}^*})^2 + (a_4^* - x_{\tilde{A}^*})^2)}{(\lambda\delta_1 + (1 - \lambda)\delta_2) - 1}}$$

Various convex combinations for trapezoidal fuzzy numbers are shown in [16]. In this study, the value of $Rank(Z) \in [-1,1]$ was calculated using $\lambda(a_2^* + a_3^*) + (1 - \lambda)(a_1^* + a_4^*)$ for $\lambda = 0.5$. Since triangular fuzzy numbers were used in this paper, $a_2 = a_3$ was taken.

As the $Rank(Z)$ value increases, so does the value of the Z-number. In other words, if u and v are Z-numbers and $Rank(u) > Rank(v)$, then u is considered greater than v .

4 SOLUTION OF THE TARGET PROBLEM IN Z-NUMBER ENVIRONMENT

In this section, the criteria weights for third-party logistics (3PL) provider selection are calculated using the dataset from the study by Erkayman et al. (2012). In the proposed approach, the elements of the original pairwise comparison matrix were transformed into Z-numbers by incorporating a reliability measure, with the second components of the Z-numbers (reliability values) being randomly assigned based on reasonable assumptions. Subsequently, the standard AHP steps were performed within the Z-number framework to compute the final weights.

4.1 Structuring of the Decision Problem:

A group of decision makers consisting of experts, managers, and academics selected 6 main criteria out of 30 possible options based on their importance. Using these selected criteria, the decision problem was modelled hierarchically as follows:

Goal: Determination of criteria weights for 3PL provider selection

Criteria: *PR:* Price

GR: General Reputation

CS: Customer Services

OD: On-time Delivery

IT: Information Technologies

FL: Flexibility

4.2 Conversion of the Pairwise Comparison Matrix to Z-Numbers

The decision makers constructed a pairwise comparison matrix to assess the relative importance of the selected criteria. This matrix reflects the comparative significance of each criterion with respect to the others. Based on Chen's fuzzy scale (as presented in Table 1), which was chosen due to its simplicity and widespread use in the 3PL and MCDM literature, the original pairwise comparison matrix was reformulated using Z-numbers, as shown in Table 2. The second components of the Z-numbers, representing the reliability of the evaluations, were assigned based on hypothetical assumptions.

Table 1 Chen's Fuzzy Scale

Linguistic variable	Fuzzy scale
Very low (VL)	(0, 0, 0.1)
Low (L)	(0, 0.1, 0.3)
Medium low (ML)	(0.1, 0.3, 0.5)
Medium (M)	(0.3, 0.5, 0.7)
Medium high (MH)	(0.5, 0.7, 0.9)
High (H)	(0.7, 0.9, 1)
Very high (VH)	(0.9, 1, 1)

4.3 Normalization of the Matrix

The sum of the Z-number values in each column is calculated separately. Then, each element is divided by the sum of its corresponding column to normalize the matrix. Based on the column-wise summation of the Z-number values in Table 2, the following results were obtained:

PR column: [(2.0746,2.7500,4.3524),(0.0358,0.3241,0.8687)]

GR column: [(6.7500,8.7857,10.8333),(0.0404,0.3575,0.7099)]

CS column: [(6.0000,8.1667,10.5000),(0.0045,0.0449,0.4027)]

OD column: [(4.5714,5.8333,7.3000),(0.0273,0.2633,0.6330)]

IT column: [(5.6500,7.2857,9.0000),(0.0126,0.1237,0.6999)]

FL column: [(7.5667,9.1667,11.6667),(0.0041,0.0409,0.3699)]

The normalization matrix, obtained by dividing each element by the sum of its corresponding column, is presented in Table 3.

Table 2 Pairwise Comparison Matrix of Criteria Expressed with Z-Numbers

	PR	GR	CS	OD	IT	FL
PR	–	[(1.5,2,2.5),ML]	[(1,1.5,2),MH]	[(0.5,1,1.5),H]	[(2.5,3,3.5),VH]	[(3.5,4,4.5),VL]
GR	[(0.4,0.5,0.67),ML]	–	[(0.5,0.67,1),M]	[(3,3.5,4),L]	[(0.25,0.29,0.33),VH]	[(0.5,0.67,1),L]
CS	[(0.5,0.67,1),MH]	[(1,1.5,2),M]	–	[(0.29,0.33,0.4),ML]	[(0.4,0.5,0.67),VL]	[(0.67,1,2),M]
OD	[(0.67,1,2),H]	[(0.25,0.29,0.33),L]	[(2.5,3,3.5),ML]	–	[(1,1.5,2),MH]	[(2.5,3,3.5),H]
IT	[(0.29,0.33,0.4),VH]	[(3,3.5,4),VH]	[(1.5,2,2.5),VL]	[(0.5,0.67,1),MH]	–	[(0.4,0.5,0.67),ML]
FL	[(0.22,0.25,0.29),VL]	[(1,1.5,2),L]	[(0.5,1,1.5),M]	[(0.29,0.33,4),H]	[(1.5,2,2.5),ML]	–

Table 3 Normalized Pairwise Comparison Matrix of Z-Number-Based Criteria Weights

	PR	GR	CS	OD	IT	FL
PR	–	[(0.1385,0.2276,0.3704), (0.0807,0.4216,0.6449)]	[(0.0952,0.1837,0.3333), (0.0106,0.3839,0.6038)]	[(0.0685,0.1714,0.3281), (0.0871,0.6110,0.8290)]	[(0.2778,0.4118,0.6195), (0.0226,0.4993,0.7933)]	[(0.3000,0.4364,0.5947), (0.0025,0.1217,0.2340)]
GR	[(0.0919,0.1818,0.3213), (0.0531,0.4530,0.6936)]	–	[(0.0476,0.0816,0.1667), (0.0119,0.3867,0.5976)]	[(0.4110,0.6000,0.8750), (0.0232,0.3070,0.5231)]	[(0.0278,0.0392,0.0590), (0.0217,0.4853,0.7841)]	[(0.0429,0.0727,0.1322), (0.0093,0.2174,0.3935)]
CS	[(0.1149,0.2424,0.4820), (0.0650,0.5969,0.9095)]	[(0.0923,0.1707,0.2963), (0.1009,0.5339,0.7637)]	–	[(0.0391,0.0571,0.0875), (0.0483,0.4054,0.6488)]	[(0.0444,0.0686,0.1180), (0.0020,0.0993,0.1894)]	[(0.0571,0.1091,0.2643), (0.0174,0.4409,0.6418)]
OD	[(0.1532,0.3636,0.9640), (0.0943,0.6619,0.9350)]	[(0.0231,0.0325,0.0494), (0.0258,0.3221,0.5341)]	[(0.2381,0.3673,0.5833), (0.0077,0.2950,0.5094)]	–	[(0.1111,0.2059,0.3540), (0.0321,0.5715,0.8334)]	[(0.2143,0.3273,0.4626), (0.0069,0.2924,0.5081)]
IT	[(0.0656,0.1212,0.1928), (0.0453,0.5328,0.9012)]	[(0.2769,0.3984,0.5926), (0.0685,0.5031,0.7917)]	[(0.1429,0.2449,0.4167), (0.0022,0.1074,0.2051)]	[(0.0685,0.1143,0.2188), (0.0756,0.5531,0.7939)]	–	[(0.0343,0.0545,0.0881), (0.0090,0.3064,0.5157)]
FL	[(0.0391,0.0715,0.1283), (0.0003,0.1971,0.4062)]	[(0.0923,0.1707,0.2963), (0.0177,0.2502,0.4353)]	[(0.0476,0.1224,0.2500), (0.0135,0.4179,0.6321)]	[(0.0391,0.0571,0.0875), (0.0492,0.4704,0.7406)]	[(0.1667,0.2745,0.4425), (0.0272,0.4135,0.6417)]	–

4.4 Calculation of the Weight Vector

The arithmetic mean of the normalized values in each row is calculated to determine the weight of the corresponding criterion. While computing the arithmetic mean of Z-numbers, the arithmetic mean of the first components (the triangular fuzzy numbers) is taken, and the second components are retained unchanged, in accordance with Zadeh’s extension principle. The resulting Z-number valued criteria weights are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4 Criteria Weights Calculated Using Z-Numbers

Criteria	Z-Numbered Weight
$Z - W_{PR}$	[(0.1760,0.2862,0.4492),(0.0112,0.4562,0.6871)]
$Z - W_{GR}$	[(0.1242,0.1951,0.3108),(0.0376,0.4957,0.7133)]
$Z - W_{CS}$	[(0.0696,0.1296,0.2496),(0.0230,0.6231,0.8173)]
$Z - W_{OD}$	[(0.1479,0.2593,0.4827),(0.0285,0.6715,0.8468)]
$Z - W_{IT}$	[(0.1176,0.1867,0.3018),(0.0073,0.3288,0.5495)]
$Z - W_{FL}$	[(0.0794,0.1431,0.2428),(0.0258,0.5500,0.7492)]

5 CONCLUSION

In this study, the classical AHP method was integrated with Z-numbers and applied to determine the criteria weights in the third-party logistics (3PL) provider selection problem. The primary aim of the study is to observe the effects of incorporating Z-numbers into the AHP methodology. For this reason, the fundamental steps of the classical AHP were adopted, and Z-numbers were integrated into this framework. The relative importance of the six main criteria identified by the decision makers was evaluated using the pairwise comparison matrix presented in the original study, while uncertainty and reliability components were incorporated into the model through the use of Z-numbers.

The obtained Z-numbered weights were ranked using the method proposed by Ezadi et al. (2018), denoted as Rank($Z-W_{Criteria}$), and the resulting ranking (Z-Ranking) was compared with both the Z-number-based ranking obtained in this study and the fuzzy ranking (Fuzzy-Ranking) reported by Erkayman et al. (2012) in the original article. The corresponding values and rankings for the relevant criteria are presented in Table 5.

Table 5 Ranking Values of Criteria Weights Based on Z-Numbers

Criteria	Rank($Z-W_{Criteria}$)	Z-Ranking	Fuzzy-Ranking
$Z-W_{PR}$	0.527504734587752	2	2
$Z-W_{GR}$	0.520255823222019	3	4
$Z-W_{CS}$	0.515800696807741	5	6
$Z-W_{OD}$	0.533379127220045	1	1
$Z-W_{IT}$	0.513771115677909	6	3
$Z-W_{FL}$	0.515801833686269	4	5

The results demonstrate that the ranking obtained using Z-numbers is largely consistent with the ranking derived from the classical fuzzy AHP approach. In particular, “On-time Delivery (OD)” and “Price (PR)” emerged as the two most important criteria in both the Z-number and fuzzy-based rankings. While minor differences were observed among the remaining criteria, the overall consistency of the ranking structure was maintained.

In this study, the consistency ratio (CR) was calculated using the classical AHP methodology, and the central value of the first component of the obtained CR was found to be 0.0753. This value is below the commonly accepted threshold of 0.10. However, since the pairwise comparison matrix was ultimately expressed in terms of Z-numbers, the direct interpretation of the CR value within the Z-number framework remains an open research question. Therefore, although the calculated CR indicates an acceptable level of consistency in the original matrix, there is a need to develop a comprehensive consistency assessment method specifically designed for Z-number-based AHP.

The findings indicate that, with the use of Z-numbers, not only precise and fuzzy values but also the degree of confidence associated with uncertain information can be incorporated into the decision-making process, thereby enabling a more sensitive and realistic evaluation. The ability of Z-numbers to simultaneously account for both uncertainty and reliability makes the method a suitable tool for addressing complex decision problems in various sectors.

For future research, the applicability of the proposed Z-AHP approach can be explored not only in the logistics sector but also in healthcare, supplier risk assessment, and other areas requiring multi-criteria decision making. Additionally, the impact of different reliability assignment strategies and diverse decision-maker profiles on the model can be examined in detail.

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